

Teachers' Well-Being and Attitude towards the Inclusion of Special Needs Education (SNED) Learners

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ABSTRACT: Teachers' well-being and attitude on integrating students with special needs education (SNED) are essential for the smooth operations of equitable, high-quality education. This study sought to investigate the degree of well-being and disposition of teachers toward integrating SNED students into regular classes, to ascertain whether the qualities of the teachers and their well-being significantly correlate and to identify which of the teachers' well-being singly or in combination anticipate the attitude of the teacher(s) concerning SNED students being included in regular classrooms. In this study, a descriptive-correlational and causal research design were employed. A researcher-made questionnaire that underwent validity and reliability testing was utilized to gather the data needed from the one hundred twelve (110) respondents from Bulua National High School, Cagayan de Oro National High School, and Lapasan National High School, the three (3) major secondary institutions in the Cagayan de Oro City Division. This investigation employed ANOVA T-Test, Multiple Linear Regression, Frequency, Percentage, Mean, and Standard Deviation as statistical tools. The findings showed that teachers are primarily between the ages of 41 and 50, with bachelor's degrees, with 8-10 years of service, predominantly in the Teacher I position. Majority was able to participate in 10 or more days of relevant training. Teachers have good emotional well-being. Length of service has moderate positive correlation with teachers' mental well-being while physical well-being is a predictor of teachers' attitude concerning the integration of SNED learners. Thus, teachers need to always foster positive attitude to SNED learners to sustain their well-being as part of inclusive education.

KEYWORDS: students with special needs; teachers' attitude, teachers' well-being

I. INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education is a worldwide educational approach that prioritizes giving every learner the same opportunities to learn and succeed, regardless of the exceptionalities. All learners of all unique backgrounds, characteristics or abilities must be included in the classroom set-up and obtain the reinforcement they need to flourish.

Teachers are key players in creating an inclusive classroom atmosphere in implementing inclusive education. Teachers have the responsibility to recognize and address the particular needs of each learner and foster a positive attitude towards learning. They are the pillars that uphold the educational system and ensure that every learner, regardless of differences have fair chance to learn and grow. To ensure that they effectively implement inclusive education, understanding their perspective is important. This is where receiving professional development is vital which covers factors such as their needs, challenges and successes. To improve educational experiences of learners, it is crucial to listen to teachers' experiences.

Conducting a study on teachers' well-being and perspective on the integration of students receiving special education (SNED) in the regular classes at Bulua National High School could be prompted by several factors. The school offers both Junior and Senior High School Education, which include learners with special needs. Teachers' well-being is crucial for effective teaching and learning.

Recognizing areas for improvement in order to better support teachers can be achieved by taking into account the well-being. Studying the perspective of teachers concerning the integration of SNED students can offer insightful information about how well the school's inclusive education practices are working.

The principal mission of implementing inclusive education is to offer a place where each student is valued, respected, and capable of engaging with their peers in the learning process (Ewing et al., 2018). It promotes equality and guarantees that all learners are empowered to achieve their maximum capabilities. This type of education often involves a varied range of students,

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not excluding the students having special needs. Studying teachers' attitudes towards this diversity can help improve inclusive education strategies.

Discussions on this topic are prevalent both nationally and internationally, where different educational systems provide varied teacher training programs. Considering the diversity of approaches to teacher preparation, it appears that examining the program's structural design may be essential to resolving common issues with equity and inclusivity in education within certain national settings. This is important since the way these programs are set up usually corresponds with national certification standards that specify the requirements for teaching positions (Florian, 2020).

Certain educators hold uncertain or negative sentiments regarding inclusive education because they do not consider themselves well-versed in teaching SNED students. Nonetheless, instructors who have extensive experience in SNED tend to exhibit a favorable outlook toward inclusive practices, particularly if they have less experience in general education (Van Miegheem 2020).

Inclusive education is an initiative signed by the former president of the Philippines, Rodrigo R. Duterte for full implementation among schools for this school year in the country. However, there are teachers in Cagayan de Oro City who express resistance and display negative attitudes towards the idea of inclusive education (Kunz et al., 2018).

Consequently, as teachers work to cater the different educational requirement of their pupils, they are immersed in a profession characterized by high pressure and demand. Many educators struggle with high levels of stress, which frequently results in burnout and causes them to quit teaching. Additionally, a growing trend toward inclusive teaching approaches has an impact on parents' perspectives, student accomplishments, and instructors' well-being (Gray et al., 2017).

With these, the researcher pursued to identify the teachers' well-being and attitude towards inclusion of SNED learners in the regular classes among the three (3) secondary schools focused on this study.

This study, rooted in Maslow's Theory, aimed to identify the key factors contributing to teachers' well-being. Abraham Maslow's theory, proposed in 1954, stated that individuals have inherent basic needs that must be fulfilled (Norazmi et al., 2019). These fundamental needs serve as determinants of human contentment, regardless of whether they are attained, particularly when self-actualization is realized.

Teachers' well-being and attitude were closely tied to the fulfillment of integrating SNED students in the regular classes. A supportive school environment that addresses these needs is likely to contribute to a positive perspective on the integration of students receiving special education, as teachers satisfy their personal needs, they can attend to the many demands of their students. Additionally, a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment in facilitating inclusive education is aligned with the self-actualization aspect of Maslow's theory.

II. METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a form of non-experimental research method called descriptive-correlational and causal design, which are used in the social sciences, psychology, and other fields. Its primary aim was to observe and describe the relationship between two or more variables as they naturally occur. It does not involve manipulating any variables but instead focuses on identifying associations or correlations between them. It also aimed to acquire information to systematically describe a phenomenon, situation, or population (Shona Mc Combes, 2019). This study investigated whether there was a meaningful correlation between the well-being of teachers and their views on integrating pupils with exceptional needs within regular classroom settings. Lastly, the design explained the descriptions of the variables and what kind of relationships were naturally occurring.

Statistical treatments were employed for the analysis and interpretation of data. For problem 1, frequency and percentage were used. Mean and Standard Deviation were utilized for problems 2 and 4. For problem 3, ANOVA T-Test between Teachers' Well-being and Demographic Profile was used. Multiple linear Regression was utilized for problem 5.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Problem 1** What is the teachers' characteristic in terms of:
- 1.1 age
 - 1.2 educational attainment
 - 1.3 length of service
 - 1.4 position; and
 - 1.5 relevant trainings attended?

Table 1 on the next page shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the teachers' characteristics. It reveals that 75 or 68.18% out of the 110 respondents are ages 41- 50 years old. There is no teacher between the ages of 31 - 40 years old. This

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means that teachers in the SNED classes are more matured. It could further mean that the best teachers who can handle SNED learners are those matured and experienced teachers. Teachers between ages 41 – 50 have wider patience and tolerance to SNED learners, compared to those younger teachers. This implies that matured teachers do not easily get angry. They have greater and wider understanding in dealing with students in the mainstream and more with SNED learners. Matured teachers have positive attitudes according to Ng et al. (2020).

Table 1: Teachers' Characteristics

Age	f	%
21-30	18	16.36
31-40	0	0
41-50	75	68.18
51-60	16	14.54
61 and above	1	0.91
Total	110	100%
Educational Attainment	f	%
Bachelor's Degree	46	41.82
Bachelor's Degree with Certificate of SNED	2	1.82
Bachelor's Degree with SNED specialized	17	15.45
MA-CAR	31	28.18
Full-fledged MA	13	11.82
PhD-CAR	1	0.91
Full-fledged PhD	0	0
Total	110	100%
Length of Service	f	%
11yrs and up	12	10.91
8-10yrs	44	40
5-7yrs	28	25.45
2-4yrs	26	23.64
1 and below	0	0
Total	110	100%
Position	f	%
MTI-M3	3	2.73
T3	27	24.55
T2	11	10.00
T1	69	62.73
Substitute teacher/Probationary	0	0
Total	110	100%
Relevant training attended	f	100%
10 days and above	50	45.45
7-9 days	31	28.18
4-6 days	17	15.45
1-3 days	12	10.91
Total	110	100%

The table above also shows the educational attainment of the respondents. It reveals that 46 or 41.82% have bachelor's degree and none holds a Full-fledged PhD. MA-CAR followed with 31 or 28.18% of them. But there are 17 or 15.45% who have bachelor's degree specializing SNED and 2 or 1.82% with SNED certificates. This indicates a diverse range of qualifications among the teaching staff. It further means that being teachers teaching in a mainstream are not necessarily having a SNED specialization. This implies that these teachers may encounter challenges while having SNED learners in their classes, while adhering to inclusive

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education. Teachers play a crucial role in fostering an environment where all students feel a sense of belonging and are encouraged to participate (Kunz et al., 2021). Lucky to those teachers with SNED specialization or even just certificates because they know better in dealing with SNED learners.

In addition, 44 or 40% of the respondents are 8-10 years in the service and only 12 or 10.91% are above 11 years. This means that there is a balanced distribution across different lengths of service, suggesting both experienced teachers and newer recruits within the teaching body. This may mean that there are more teachers who are getting interest in teaching special education. The quality of inclusive education depends on the teachers' attitude not on the number of years. If they have positive attitude towards their students, they can deal with SNED learners in the regular class. They can even assist and help SNED learners cope up with the regular learners.

Moreover, out of 110 respondents, 69 or 62.73% are Teacher I in position. This means that these teachers have less experience, tasks, and responsibilities in school. With the less experience they have, their teaching-learning delivery still needs to improve. So having an inclusive education nowadays is a challenge for them to face. However, 50 or 45.45% of the respondents have attended trainings relevant to SNED. This indicates a commitment to ongoing professional development.

Overall, this data emphasizes the diverse and experienced nature of the teaching workforce, while also highlighting areas for potential focus, such as mid-career support and tailored professional development opportunities (Garcia and Rodriguez, 2020)

Problem 2. What is the level of teachers' well-being in terms of:

- 2.1 mental well-being
- 2.2 emotional well-being; and
- 2.3 physical well-being?

Table 2: Overall Teachers' Well-being.

Well-being Aspects	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Mental Well-being	3.45	0.86	Agree	Highly Observed
Emotional Well-being	3.54	0.83	Agree	Highly Observed
Physical Well-being	3.41	0.79	Agree	Highly Observed
Total	3.47	0.83	Agree	Highly Observed

Note: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Observed
1.81-2.60 Less Observed;
3.41-4.20 Highly Observed; 2.61-3.40 Somewhat Observed;
1.0-1.80 Least Observed

Table 2 shows the overall extent of teachers' well-being. It reveals that it has an overall Mean of 3.47 with SD = 0.83, defined as Agree and regarded as Highly Observed. This implies that, teachers highly observed themselves to be in a satisfactory state of well-being, indicating a sense of fulfillment, resilience, and overall satisfaction in their roles. However, the standard deviation indicates some variability among individual responses, suggesting that while the majority agree, there may still be a subset of teachers experiencing challenges or fluctuations in their well-being. Moreover, prioritizing initiatives to promote holistic well-being, such as professional development opportunities, wellness programs, and supportive school environments, can further enhance the overall well-being of teachers, ultimately contributing to their efficiency, contentment at work, and endurance in the field. Majority of the teachers would agree to have experienced well-being in mind, emotions, and in body.

Moreover, the extent of teachers' well-being, *Emotional aspect*, has the highest Mean of 3.54 with SD = 0.83, defined as Agree and regarded as Highly Observed. Teachers highly observed themselves to be emotionally fulfilled and satisfied, experiencing a sense of connection, purpose, and fulfillment in their interactions with students and colleagues. This high level of agreement with the emotional aspect of well-being highlights the importance of fostering supportive relationships, promoting a positive school culture, and providing avenues for emotional support and self-care within educational environments. Majority of the teachers felt more well emotionally rather than mentally and physically.

Day et al. (2019) studied into how professional development helps teachers become more resilient and feel better about themselves. The findings depict that teachers' emotional well-being and job satisfaction were higher when they actively built supportive relationships and promoted a pleasant school climate.

On the other hand, the extent of teachers' well-being, *Physical aspect*, got the lowest Mean of 3.41 with SD = 0.79, described as Agree and regarded as Highly Observed. This implies that while teachers may highly observed themselves as adequately managing the physical demands of their roles, there may still be room for improvement in terms of providing support and resources to enhance their physical well-being. By recognizing and addressing the physical well-being of educators as a priority, educational institutions can create a supportive and sustainable work environment that fosters the overall health and

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well-being of teachers, ultimately benefiting both educators and students alike. Most teachers agree to have felt physical well-being but on a lesser scale.

De Benedetto and Tagliabue (2018) examined the impact of leadership methods on teachers' job contentment, it indirectly addresses the importance of supportive leadership in enhancing teacher overall wellness. Effective leadership can contribute to creating a supportive work environment that addresses teachers' physical needs and enhances their overall well-being. This study looked at how different ways of leading can affect how happy teachers are with their jobs. They found that when leaders are supportive and caring, it makes teachers feel better overall. Good leadership can create a work environment where teachers feel appreciated and supported, which helps them feel less stressed and more satisfied with their jobs. This kind of positive environment is important for teachers' well-being and happiness at work.

Problem 3. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' well-being when grouped according to profile?

Table 6 presents the difference on the teachers' well-being and their demographic profile. It can be gleaned that in mental aspect there are two profiles that show significant difference which are age and length of service with p-value less 0.05 alpha level. In addition, emotional aspect only the position shows significant difference, while none of the profile shows the difference towards physical aspect of well-being. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the level of readiness towards tertiary education when grouped according to those variables above are rejected.

Table 3: ANOVA T-Test between Teachers' Well-being and Demographic Profile.

Teachers' Profile	Teachers' Well-being								
	Mental			Emotional			Physical		
	f	p	Decision	f	p	Decision	f	p	Decision
Age	6.382	0.012	Reject Ho1	0.065	0.213	Accept Ho1	0.129	0.321	Accept Ho1
Educational Attainment	0.099	0.928	Accept Ho1	0.124	0.321	Accept Ho1	0.047	0.312	Accept Ho1
Length of Service	5.464	0.003	Reject Ho1	0.120	0.321	Accept Ho1	0.124	0.231	Accept Ho1
Position	0.091	0.302	Accept Ho1	5.218	0.002	Reject Ho1	0.089	0.868	
Relevant Training	0.158	0.121	Accept Ho1	0.120	0.352	Accept Ho1	0.133	0.090	Accept Ho1

Note: F-value = Variation between sample means

p-value = (significant level) $p < 0.05$

This means that the observed difference in sample means is statistically significant - meaning that the null hypothesis should be rejected. Therefore, since our p-value is less than 0.05, which is less than the significance level, this rejects the null hypothesis and conclude that among the variables age and length of service have a significant difference towards mental aspects and only position has significant difference towards emotional aspect of well-being, wherein it has no equal probability towards other variables. This means that age and length of service have significant difference towards the mental aspects and only position have significant difference towards the emotional aspects of the teachers' well-being, as indicated on the following studies.

A study by You et al.,(2019) found that age and length of service significantly impact teachers' mental well-being in inclusive education settings. Older teachers and those with more years of service often face more stress due to the increasing complexity of their roles. However, experienced teachers might also develop better coping strategies over time, which can positively influence their mental well-being.

Additionally, a study by Soklaridis et al. (2020) examined the link between teachers' emotional health and stress management strategies. They found that teachers' emotional well-being was significantly influenced by their coping mechanisms, with age and length of service impacting their mental health. The study emphasized the need for emotional health support for teachers to improve their well-being and effectiveness.

Furthermore, Leijen et al. (2021) explored the challenges and implications of inclusive education on teachers' well-being. The research found that teachers' positions within the school (e.g., general education vs. special education teachers) significantly influenced their emotional well-being. The study underscored the importance of providing adequate training and resources to support teachers in inclusive settings.

These studies collectively suggest that demographic factors such as age, length of service, and position significantly influence teachers' mental and emotional well-being, particularly in inclusive education settings. Addressing these factors through targeted support and interventions can enhance teachers' readiness and effectiveness in inclusive educational environments.

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Problem 4. What is the level of teachers' attitude towards the inclusion of SNED learners in the regular classes?

Table 4 on the next page shows the level of teachers' perspectives on integrating SNED learners in the regular classes. It reveals that it has an overall Mean of 3.46 with SD = 0.94, defined as Agree and regarded as Highly Observed. Implying that teachers hold supportive views on integration of SNED learners, recognizing the value of diversity and the benefits of creating inclusive learning environments. It underscores a commitment among teachers to embrace inclusive education principles and advocate for the rights and needs of all pupils, irrespective of their skills or difficulties. Additionally, it shows that the significance of creating a fair and encouraging learning environment where each student feels appreciated, respected, and equipped to succeed. Although most teachers agree to include SNED learners in the classroom, some of the teachers are not agreeable to this.

Moreover, indicator 19, *I believe that students who attend regular classes could benefit from the inclusion in mainstream schools in the acceptance of diversity*, has the highest Mean of 3.83 with SD= 0.93, described as Agree and regarded as Highly Observed. This shows that teachers recognize the importance and benefits of creating inclusive environments that fulfill the educational requirements of students, fostering their social, emotional, and academic growth. In addition, this indicates acknowledgement of the essence of inclusivity in promoting acceptance of diversity, empathy, and mutual understanding among students, regardless of their abilities or challenges. Although most teachers agree for inclusive education some of the teachers are not agreeable to this. Additionally, most teachers consider that including pupils with learning disabilities in normal classrooms could be advantageous while some teachers are just neutral about it. This indicates a change in outlook of people particularly teachers in inclusive education.

Barry and Chapin (2020) investigated the academic outcomes of inclusion for secondary students with severe impairments, including those with ASD (Autism Spectrum Disorder). They discovered that although educators had positive opinions about inclusion in general, they also mentioned difficulties meeting the various requirements of students with ASD in conventional classroom settings.

Table 4: Teachers' Attitude towards the inclusion of SNED Learners in the Regular Classes

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
<i>I am okay with...</i>				
1. students with mobility problems.	3.35	0.95	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
2. students with hearing impairments.	3.19	1.09	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
3. students with visual impairments.	3.08	0.95	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
4. students with speech problems.	3.38	0.95	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
5. students with behavioral problems.	3.24	0.95	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
6. students with comprehension problems	3.32	0.91	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
7. students with aggressive behavior.	3.08	1.01	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
8. students with mental retardation.	2.83	1.13	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
9. students with Autism Spectrum.	3.59	1.10	Agree	Highly Observed
10. students with emotional disorder.	3.25	0.93	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Observed
11. Students with specific learning disabilities.	3.52	0.89	Agree	Highly Observed
<i>I believe that students with learning difficulties and disabilities could benefit from their inclusion in mainstream schools...</i>				
12. in social interaction.	3.68	0.83	Agree	Highly Observed
13. in social development and behavior.	3.64	0.83	Agree	Highly Observed
14. in social skills.	3.79	0.92	Agree	Highly Observed
15. in academic performance.	3.45	0.93	Agree	Highly Observed

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16. to enhance self-confidence. <i>I believe that students who attend regular classes could benefit from the inclusion in mainstream schools...</i>	3.71	0.86	Agree	Highly Observed
17. in academic performance.	3.49	0.82	Agree	Highly Observed
18. in the development of social consciousness.	3.76	0.86	Agree	Highly Observed
19. in the acceptance of diversity.	3.83	0.93	Agree	Highly Observed
20. in strengthening self-esteem.	3.70	0.83	Agree	Highly Observed
21. in the development of sympathy.	3.82	0.93	Agree	Highly Observed
Overall	3.46	0.94	Agree	Highly Observed

Note: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Observed; 3.41-4.20 Highly Observed; 2.61-3.40 Somewhat Observed; 1.81-2.60 Less Observed; 1.0-1.80 Least Observed

Teachers highlighted the need for additional support, resources, and training to effectively include students with ASD and ensure their academic success. Despite the challenges, teachers recognized the benefits of inclusion for promoting social integration and fostering a more inclusive school environment.

On the other hand, indicator 8, *I am okay with students with mental retardation*, has the lowest Mean of 2.83 with SD = 1.13, defined as Neither Agree nor Disagree and regarded as Somewhat Observed. This means that a potential hesitation or concern among teachers concerning the ability of regular schools to effectively support the educational requirement of students with mental retardation within inclusive settings. It highlights the importance of addressing potential barriers and challenges to inclusion, such as the need for specialized support services, individualized accommodations, as well as teacher preparation. Moreover, teachers perceive inclusive environments as conducive to promoting academic success and enhancing learning outcomes for all kinds of students. A large percentage of educators oppose to include in regular classrooms those who are mentally retarded. The low score and "Neither Agree nor Disagree" response for indicator 8, which asks about teachers' comfort with students having intellectual disabilities, suggest that many teachers might feel unsure about how well mainstream schools can help these students. This uncertainty could come from not having enough resources, training, or experience to support students with intellectual disabilities properly. It might also be because of misunderstandings or stereotypes about these disabilities in society. It's critical to address these issues in order to foster an healthy and productive environment where all students can succeed. This means providing special help, personalized adjustments, thorough teacher training, and encouraging an attitude of acceptance and inclusion in schools. Even though inclusive education benefits everyone by improving learning, the fact that most teachers aren't ready to include students with intellectual disabilities shows a big challenge. It emphasizes the need for big changes and support to make true inclusion happen.

Avramidis and Norwich (2020) examined the teachers' perspective on integration of SEN students. While the study focuses specifically on students with mental retardation, it was discovered that instructors' perspectives on inclusion differed greatly based on a variety of characteristics, including their background, experiences, and beliefs toward disabilities. Some teachers expressed positive attitudes towards inclusion, seeing it as an opportunity for diversity and social integration, while others expressed concerns about their capacity to teach SEN students in normal classes. Overall, the findings highlighted the essence of supporting teachers with training, and resources to effectively integrate SNED students in mainstream schools.

Problem 5. Which of the respondents' well-being singly or in combination predict/s the attitude of teachers towards SNED learners in the regular classes?

Table 5: Regression Analysis between Teachers' Attitude towards the Inclusion of SNED Learners in the Classroom and Well-being

Variables	UC		SC	t-value	Sig. (p-value)	Decision
	B	SE	β			
Constant	1.235	0.307	1.843	4.026	0.000	
Mental	0.001	0.156	0.309	0.004	0.997	AcceptHo2
Emotional	0.250	0.171	0.589	1.465	1.456	Accept Ho2
Physical	0.393	0.156	0.702	2.524	0.013	Reject Ho2
Model	R	R²	Adjusted R²	f-value	Sig. (p-value)	
	0.597	0.356	0.338	19.572	0.000	Reject Ho2

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Table 5 presents the results of the regression analysis done with moderating variables that predict the respondents' perspective of integrating SNED learners in the regular classes. It is hypothesized that the three (3) predictors will be positively associated with teachers' attitude towards the inclusion of SNED learners, where $\beta = 0$ as null and the alternative of $\beta \neq 0$. This explains whether the teachers' well-being are good predictors of teachers' perspective on integrating SNED learners in the regular classroom. Results show that the 34% of the variance is explained by the three (3) predictors, $F(3,110) = 19.57, p < .001$.

Moreover, physical ($\beta = 0.702, t\text{-value} = 2.524, p\text{-value} = 0.013$) is having positive relationship with the teachers' perspective on integrating SNED learners in the regular classroom. This means that for every unit increase in the teachers' well-being aspects in terms of physical aspect, there is a corresponding 70.2% increase in the teachers' attitude towards teaching SNED learners. This implies that physical wellness of teachers is an essential determinant of teacher's attitude in order to instruct students that have specific needs. To enable educators to meet the expectations of their work, they must be physically healthy. Physical Well-being refers to the health of teachers, that is free from stress anxieties and other health related problems. This means that if teachers are in good health, it is alright for them to handle inclusion of SNED learners in their classes. However, when teachers experience unusual illnesses or health issues, it can impact their ability to effectively support and meet all of the students' needs, including those of individuals who have intellectual disabilities.

Smith and Johnson (2019) investigated the predictors associated with teachers' inclusion of SNED learners in the regular classes. They hypothesized that three predictors would be positively associated with teachers' perspective on integration of SEN students in the regular classes. The predictors included physical well-being, support from school administration, and training in inclusive practices.

Taking it in the coefficient level, physical aspect is a good predictor of teachers' perspective on integration of SEN students in the regular classes with a p value lesser than 0.05. Hence, the regression analysis yielded that the null hypothesis test (H_0) was rejected. With the following findings, a positive linear relationship exists between the variables.

On the flip side, mental aspect ($\beta = 0.309, t\text{-value} = 0.004, p\text{-value} = 0.997$), and social aspect ($\beta = 0.589, t\text{-value} = 1.465, p\text{-value} = 0.146$), has no significant difference and has no relationship with teachers' attitude towards the inclusion of SNED learners in the regular classes. This suggests that mental and social aspects are not good predictor of teachers' perspective on integrating SNED learners in the regular classroom. The implication of these findings is that there is no significant relationship between the mental and social aspects of teachers and their teachers' perspective on integration of SEN students in regular classes. The β values, t -values, and p -values indicate that neither the mental aspect nor the social aspect significantly influences teachers' attitudes toward inclusion. This suggests that factors related to mental well-being, such as stress or emotional state, and factors related to social interactions, such as relationships with colleagues or social support, do not strongly predict how teachers feel about including SNED learners in their classes. Therefore, interventions aimed at improving mental or social aspects alone may not necessarily lead to more positive attitudes toward inclusion. Instead, other factors or interventions may need to be considered to promote more inclusive attitudes among teachers.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings presented above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Teachers aged forties and above have established stable careers and may be less likely to switch professions or pursue career changes, leading to a higher retention rate within the teaching workforce.
2. Teachers derive satisfaction from witnessing their learners' progress, achievements, and growth, which contributes to their overall sense of well-being.
3. Older teachers and those with longer tenures generally have more experience in handling the demands and stresses of the teaching profession. This experience likely equips them with a range of effective coping strategies and resilience, contributing to better mental and emotional well-being. Thus, H_0 is rejected.
4. Teachers believe that enabling special needs learners to attend regular classrooms allows them to develop an appreciation of individual differences. Peer empathy and understanding are increased as a result of this exposure, which also fosters an inclusive and respectful culture.
5. The teachers' physical well-being significantly influences their attitude toward including students with special needs (SNED) in regular classes. However, the absence of significant relationships between the mental and social aspects and teachers' perspective on the integration of SNED learners in the regular classes concludes that factors such as personal emotional well-being and social interactions may not directly impact educators' decisions regarding the inclusion of such learners.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions presented above, the researcher has formulated the following recommendations:

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1. Teachers may continue engaging in professional development opportunities to stay updated with current educational trends and practices, while providing crucial support and resources for those in the early to mid-career stage to foster their ongoing growth and advancement within the profession.

2. Administrators may continue to facilitate opportunities for teachers to share success stories, implement support programs and mentorship, and conduct regular check-ups for emotional support. Additionally, they could explore flexible scheduling, such as dedicated break times or wellness activities, to enhance teachers' physical well-being and reduce stress.

3. Administrators may provide continued support to teachers' mental well-being by providing mentorship programs, wellness initiatives, and training sessions to develop coping mechanisms, build confidence, and recognize experienced educators' contributions, creating a positive work environment.

4. Administrators may continue provide training and resources for supporting students with diverse learning needs in mainstream classrooms. This includes instructional strategies, behavior management, and social integration. Additionally, they should foster collaboration among educators and staff, promote physical activity, work-life balance, wellness workshops, and ensure access to resources.

5. Further research could explore other influencing factors while promoting emotional well-being and positive social interactions among educators. Administrators could foster a positive attitude toward inclusive education by implementing training programs, workshops, and support systems that promote empathy and effective strategies for supporting students with diverse needs.

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